

An Experimental Examination of Foam Stability under Pressure for EPB TBM Tunneling

Yuanli Wu, Michael A. Mooney, Minsu Cha

Abstract

Foam as a soil conditioning agent has been extensively employed in earth pressure balanced (EPB) tunnel boring machines (TBM) to change the mechanical and hydraulic properties of soils for effective excavation. Foam stability is a critical parameter that influences the performance of foam and foam-conditioned soils. This paper examines foam stability under pressure through a novel foam generation – pressure chamber – foam capture testing system. A comprehensive suite of foam experiments was performed to examine the physical phenomenon of foam degradation and time-dependent foam properties under pressure. Testing results suggest that foam liquid loss is not an effective indicator for characterizing foam stability, while foam volume loss is a more appropriate measure of foam stability. Results also reveal that foam liquid drainage is significantly retarded at higher chamber pressure because foam bubbles are smaller and more uniform. Bubble size was not appreciably different in dry and wet foams.

Keywords: EPB, Soil Conditioning, Foam Stability, Pressure

1. Introduction

Foam is routinely used to modify the in-situ soil properties during excavation in EPB TBM tunneling. The desired properties of foam-conditioned soil include elasticity, high compressibility, low shearing resistance, low permeability and flowability/workability (Budach and Thewes, 2015; Milligan, 2000; Mori et al., 2018; Peila, 2014; Thewes et al., 2012; Vinai et al., 2008). When foam is homogeneously mixed with soil, the foam bubbles create particle or clod separation that transforms the in-situ soil into a compressible, elastic medium with sufficiently low permeability and greatly reduced shearing resistance. Sufficient compressibility is needed so that unavoidable changes in TBM advance rate or screw conveyor discharge rate does not translate into significant chamber pressure fluctuations (Bezuijen, 1999; Mooney et al., 2016; Mori et al., 2017; Psomas, 2002; Quebaud et al., 1998). Conditioned soil in the chamber is subjected to tens to hundreds of cycles of loading due to such advance rate/discharge fluctuations as well as potential rotation of material from lower pressure in the upper portion of the chamber/cutterhead openings to higher pressure in the lower portion of the chamber/cutterhead openings. It is therefore important that the foam behaves elastically, i.e., that plastic strain does not accumulate with loading cycles. Further, the foam serves to restrict water flow through the soil's pores.

A critical characteristic of foam in conditioned soil is its stability, i.e., the ability of foam to maintain its structure and the aforementioned properties when mixed with soil throughout residency time in the chamber. During normal operations, residency time can vary from 30-90 min depending on the diameter of the TBM, depth of the excavation chamber, advance rate, etc. Because foam stability greatly affects foam-conditioned soil behavior in EPB TBM tunneling, it is important to understand the fundamentals of foam stability in the context of EPB TBM tunneling. Schramm and Wassmuth (1994) define foam stability as the resistance to the processes of film (bubble wall) thinning and coalescence (film rupturing). In film thinning, the liquid films that separate bubbles thin and bubbles approach closely together. In coalescence, the films between bubbles rupture and bubbles merge together to form larger bubbles. Schramm and Wassmuth (1994) state that foam stability is largely determined by liquid drainage and rupture of the thin film. Quebaud et al. (1998) describe 'foam persistence' (akin to the meaning of stability) as the capacity to maintain a constant volume and keep the liquid of the matrix from flowing out. As we demonstrate later, maintaining constant volume and limiting liquid drainage are quite different behaviors.

In tunneling, foam stability is typically characterized by its foam liquid half-life, defined as the time necessary for foam to lose one-half of its initial liquid fraction due to drainage. While there is no standardized testing procedure (e.g., ASTM, DIN), the EFNARC (2005) recommends using a filter-funnel filled with 80 g foam subjected to atmospheric pressure to measure liquid drainage and determine foam liquid half-life. The EFNARC (2005) half-life (or liquid drainage) method is widely used and referenced in characterizing foam stability for soil conditioning in tunneling (Milligan, 2000; Psomas, 2002; Quebaud et al., 1998; Thewes et al., 2012).

The rationale for using liquid drainage time as a measure of foam stability for EPB soil conditioning is not well addressed in the literature, but perhaps can be related to non-tunneling based fundamental studies of foam (Rand and Kraynik, 1983; Schramm and Wassmuth, 1994). It may be, as alluded to in Quebaud's definition that the prevailing assumption is that significant liquid drainage results in significant foam volume reduction. To the author's knowledge, only one publication, by Langmaack (2009), suggests that the foam volume can be used in addition to liquid drainage since the remaining foam volume is more relevant to judge the stability of the foam-soil mixture. The author reports approximately 5% foam volume loss of two different foams over 30 minutes. Unfortunately liquid loss was not reported.

The term 'stability' implies the continuance of desired properties without change. It is unclear whether liquid drainage implies an accompanying degradation in desired engineering properties, i.e., elasticity, compressibility, etc. And, at a fundamental level, it is unclear what is physically happening to foam properties during liquid drainage. Further, the traditional liquid drainage test is conducted under atmospheric pressure, while in practice foam and foam-conditioned soils are

almost always subjected to pressure in the tool gap, excavation chamber and screw conveyor of an EPB TBM. This paper addresses these issues by examining foam stability in the context of sustained performance as described above. A comprehensive suite of experiments was conducted using a novel foam generation – chamber pressure – foam capture device testing system that allows the measurement of macroscopic and microscopic foam properties under pressures typically experienced in tunneling. The physical phenomena of liquid drainage is characterized and its relationship to foam performance is examined. Finally, the implications on tunneling practice are discussed.

2. Test Equipment

A novel foam generation – pressure chamber – foam capture device testing system was developed to perform a comprehensive suite of foam experiments. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the laboratory foam generation system and foam testing devices. A liquid flow controller and an air mass flow controller were used to produce a foam solution plus compressed air mixture with the desired foam expansion ratio (FER). The foam generator was comprised of closely packed 3 mm glass beads. The foam solution was prepared by mixing water with a commercially available surfactant at a desired concentration (c_f). In this study, $c_f = 5\%$ was used for all the foam tests. The foam solution-air mixture then flowed through a 20 cm long and 1.5 cm inside diameter laboratory-scale foam generator.

A 45 cm tall, 11.4 L pressure chamber was used to simulate the pressurized environment that exists in the tool gap, mixing chamber, and screw conveyor during EPB tunneling. Foam behavior with elapsed time, such as liquid drainage, foam and air volume loss, foam compressibility, FER , and liquid volume fraction can be measured under pressures up to 5 bar (gauge pressure). Foam was injected into the pressure chamber under a desired pressure with a controlled FER_p (the subscript p implies the chamber pressure) and foam flow rate. This was achieved by adjusting the air flow rate at the air mass flow controller such that it delivered the correct air flow to liquid flow ratio at the prescribed chamber pressure. The foam column height was constant (40 cm) for all of the pressure chamber tests in this study. The literature has shown that foam column height influences foam liquid drainage and liquid drainage-based half-life (Rand and Kraynik, 1983; Saint-Jalmes and Langevin, 2002). We verified this finding through a series of foam liquid drainage tests; the results are presented in Appendix 1.

A foam capture device was inserted immediately downstream of the foam generator to capture the generated foam for image analysis. The foam capture device, shown in Figure 2, is 5 cm in diameter and 0.6 cm thick (deep). A back-pressure regulator downstream of the foam capture device allows the capture of foam at the desired pressure, e.g., equal to the exit pressure of the generator

or equal to the chamber pressure. The device was placed on its side to incorporate gravity-driven liquid drainage in the experiment. Once captured, the foam is imaged with elapsed time using an optical microscope. The optical microscope was focused on the uppermost region of the foam sample to eliminate the influence of gravity driven liquid drainage of overlying foam. The imaging area ($1\text{ cm} \times 0.7\text{ cm}$) is shown Figure 2a. This allows detailed analysis of bubble size and bubble size distribution with elapsed time under pressure. A more detailed description of the foam capture device can be found in Mooney et al. (2016). Detailed testing procedures for the pressure chamber and foam capture tests are shown in Appendix 2.

Figure 1. Schematic of the laboratory foam generation system and foam testing devices (pressure chamber and foam capture device).

Figure 2. Schematic of the foam capture device.

3. Time Dependent Foam Behavior under Pressure

3.1 Atmospheric Pressure

A series of tests was performed to characterize foam properties with time, first at atmospheric pressure ($p = 0$ bar gauge) and then at higher pressure ($p = 2$ and 4 bar gauge). Testing included foam liquid loss (the traditional approach to measure foam stability), foam compressibility, and foam bubble size distribution over a 60 min duration. In this series, surfactant concentration $c_f = 5\%$ was used to generate foam. The foam expansion ratio was kept constant over all chamber pressures, i.e., $FER_p = 20$. Figure 3a shows the liquid volume, foam volume and air volume loss with time at atmospheric pressure. Definitions for these parameters are shown in Equation (1)-(3).

$$\text{Liquid loss} = 100 \times \frac{\Delta V_l}{V_{l,0}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Foam loss} = 100 \times \frac{\Delta V_f}{V_{f,0}} = 100 \times \frac{V_{f,0} - V_f}{V_{f,0}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Air loss} = 100 \times \frac{\Delta V_a}{V_{a,0}} = 100 \times \frac{V_{a,0} - V_a}{V_{a,0}} \quad (3)$$

where $V_{l,0}$ is the total volume of liquid for a foam sample in the chamber, $V_{l,0} = V_{f,0} / FER$, $V_{f,0}$ is the initial volume of foam in the chamber, ΔV_l is the accumulated volume of drained liquid at time t , ΔV_f is the change of foam volume at time t , V_f is the volume of foam at time t , ΔV_a is the

change of air volume at time t , $V_{a,0}$ is the initial air volume and $V_{a,t} = V_{f,0} - V_{l,t}$, and V_a is the volume of air at time t . The foam liquid drains faster in the first 40 min and slows after 40 min. The resulting foam volume loss with time is very small compared to the liquid volume loss. For example, at $t = 35$ min, 50% liquid has drained from the foam, however, the corresponding foam volume loss at this time is only 3%. At $t = 60$ min, 74% liquid has drained from the foam, but the foam volume loss is only 4%. The decrease in foam volume is very small but the liquid loss is significant. In addition, air loss during the test, calculated as foam volume loss minus liquid volume loss, was determined to be negligible (less than 2%) during the foam aging process as shown in Figure 3a, indicating that the foam loss is strictly due to the liquid loss from the foam and not due to release of air. Both liquid loss and foam loss are normalized by their maximum values, and the resulting normalized liquid and foam loss are shown in Figure 3b. The normalized liquid loss and foam loss present similar behavior over time. This is due to the negligible air loss in the foam degradation process, thus the foam loss mainly results from the liquid loss from the foam.

Figure 3. (a) Time dependent liquid, foam and air loss, and (b) normalized liquid and foam loss for $FER_0 = 20$ foam evaluated at atmospheric pressure.

To investigate the nature of time dependent liquid loss and foam loss, we examine the bubble size distribution over time. A foam sample with $FER_0 = 20$ was imaged using the foam capture device. Figure 4a shows three examples of imaged foam bubbles at $t = 0, 30, 60$ min. The images show that there is a significant increase in bubble size over time. The rate of bubble size increase is greater from $t = 0$ to 30 min than $t = 30$ to 60 min. The process of bubble size increase over time is due to coalescence and coarsening, and gravity-driven liquid drainage (Fameau and Salonen, 2014; Magrabi et al., 1999; Schramm, 1992; Weaire and Hutzler, 1999). Liquid in the foam tends to drain due to the force of gravity, thinning the bubble walls. Coalescence is the rupturing of the thin liquid film that separates two adjacent bubbles. Coarsening is the process of the growth of large bubbles at the expense of smaller bubbles and is driven by the diffusion of gas from smaller to larger bubbles. Figure 4a also shows that foam initially consisted of spherical bubbles at $t = 0$

min; thereafter, bubbles become polyhedral at $t = 30$ and 60 min due to increased liquid loss.

The bubble images were analyzed using a commercial image analysis software AmScope to obtain the area-equivalent bubble diameter D of bubbles, and the corresponding empirical foam bubble size probability and cumulative distributions (Figure 4b and c). The Weibull probability density function (PDF) was used to fit the empirical probability distributions because it provided the best fit compared to the other statistical distributions such as normal and log-normal (Magrabi et al., 1999). As shown in Figure 4b, the Weibull PDF shows a satisfactory fit to the measured bubble size distributions with elapsed time. The PDF curves reveal that the probability of smaller bubbles ($D < 0.2$ mm) decreases and the distribution becomes wider over time. Accordingly, the cumulative distribution curves shift to the right over time. These results indicate that bubbles become bigger and foam becomes less uniform in bubble size over time. Furthermore, the time evolution of average bubble diameter was determined from the bubble image analysis and the results are shown in Figure 4d. The average bubble diameter increases 120% in the initial 30 min, and the rate of bubble size growth is noticeably reduced after 30 min (only 30% increase).

Although the 2D-imaged foam degradation differs from 3D degradation (Marchalot et al., 2008), the 2D bubble images are analyzed to verify if foam liquid loss is properly reflected in the bubble images. From image analysis, the diameter and area of air bubbles in a finite image area can be obtained, and thus the area-based liquid fraction (ratio of liquid area to image area) can be calculated for each foam image. Moreover, the liquid volume fraction at each time interval, defined as the ratio of liquid volume to foam volume $\varphi = V_l/V_f$, can be determined throughout the pressure chamber test since the liquid volume and foam volume are measured. Figure 4e presents the percent decrease in liquid fraction calculated from the 3D chamber test as well as from 2D image analysis. As shown, the percent change in liquid fraction obtained from the 2D image analysis decreases with elapsed time, indicating that the bubble images capture liquid loss in foam over time. The response is not identical to that of the 3D chamber test measurements because the image analysis is unable to capture the changes in the third dimension.

Figure 4. Time dependent bubble images and bubble size analysis for $FER_0 = 20$ foam evaluated at atmospheric pressure.

Changes in FER during the pressure chamber test, here atmospheric pressure, are shown in Figure 5a. FER increases from 20 to 74 over 60 min due to continuous liquid drainage from the foam. The liquid volume fraction decreases from 0.050 to 0.014 (72% decrease) in 60 min.

The time dependent behavior of foam compressibility can also reflect the stability of a foam sample. In this study, foam compressibility was investigated by conducting cyclic loading in the pressure chamber. Foam compressibility C_{foam} is defined as the fractional volume change of foam ($\Delta V_f/V_f$) divided by the pressure change Δp , as shown in Equation (4). C_{foam} was determined by

cycling the chamber pressure 1 bar. The foam was cycled up to twelve times in 60 min. As shown in Figure 5b, C_{foam} increases with elapsed time, i.e., a 6% increase in C_{foam} from $t = 0$ to 60 min. This increase in C_{foam} is mainly due to foam liquid loss with time that reduces the incompressible liquid fraction of the foam. Therefore, the volume fraction of air in the foam increases, resulting in an increase in C_{foam} . Also shown in Figure 5b is the compressibility of air C_{air} per ideal gas law (assuming the temperature is constant during the test), as shown in Equation (5), where p_{ch} is the absolute air pressure in the chamber.

$$C_{foam} = 100 \times \frac{\Delta V_f}{V_f \times \Delta p} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{air} = 100 \times \frac{1}{p_{ch} + \Delta p} \quad (5)$$

Figure 5. (a) Changes in liquid fraction and FER with time, and (b) foam compressibility with time for foam with $FER_0 = 20$ at atmospheric pressure.

3.2 Elevated Pressure

Time dependent foam behavior (bubble size, liquid and foam loss, and compressibility) was also investigated at $p = 2$ and 4 bar. Foam was injected into the pressurized chamber while maintaining constant $FER_p = 20$ (and a separate set with $FER_p = 10$). As shown in Figure 6a, liquid volume loss rates decrease substantially with the increase in chamber pressure. For example, at $t = 30$ min, the liquid loss is 41% at $p = 0$ bar, 15% at 2 bar, and 13% at 4 bar. Figure 6b shows the measured liquid loss half-life (T_{50}) at various pressures for both $FER_p = 20$ and 10 foams. As shown, T_{50} increases with increase in chamber pressure, and the increased rate of T_{50} is more prominent (T_{50} is doubled) from 0 to 2 bar for both foams. In addition, $FER_p = 20$ constantly shows higher T_{50} than $FER_p = 10$ foam. The result suggests that drier foam has longer liquid loss half-life than wet foam. More detailed comparison for the two foams will be addressed in the later part of the paper.

Foam volume loss follows a similar trend with liquid volume loss as shown in Figure 6c, at $t = 30$ min, foam loss decreases from 2.2% at $p = 0$ bar to 0.8% at $p = 4$ bar. In addition, accumulated air volume loss are less than 1.5% as shown in Figure 6d, revealing the very small foam volume loss is due solely to foam liquid drainage. The normalized liquid volume loss and foam volume loss shown in Figure 6e reveal a more constant rate of liquid drainage with time as pressure increases.

Figure 6. Time dependent liquid, foam and air loss, and normalized liquid and foam loss for $FER_p = 20$ foam; and liquid loss half-life for $FER_p = 20$ and 10 foams at $p = 0, 2,$ and 4 bar pressures.

To understand why increased pressure reduces the rate of liquid and foam loss, foam bubbles were imaged at $p = 0, 2,$ and 4 bar with constant $FER_p = 20$. The foam bubble images over time and under pressure are shown in Figure 7. The images reveal that foam bubbles are smaller and more uniform with increased chamber pressure, even though the FER was held constant at each pressure. This can be explained by the pressure conditions in the foam generator that is strongly dependent on chamber pressure. Higher chamber pressure translates into higher pressure upstream in the foam generator. As shown by Mooney et al. (2017), bubble size generated is a function of fluid velocity through the generator, bead size in the generator, and pressure in the generator. Here, the increased foam generator pressure produces smaller bubbles.

Figure 7. Bubble images with elapsed time for $FER_p = 20$ foam at $p = 0, 2,$ and 4 bar gauge pressures.

Figure 8 shows the bubble size analysis results for foam at $t = 0$ and 60 min under pressure. Both the Weibull distribution fitted bubble size PDFs (Figure 8a) and the empirical cumulative distributions (Figure 8b) show that there is a greater portion of smaller bubbles ($D < 0.2$ mm) at higher chamber pressures, and the bubble size distribution is narrower (more uniform) at higher pressures. After 60 min, bubble sizes increase significantly at all three pressures, but bubbles at $p = 4$ bar are still noticeably smaller than those at 0 and 2 bar. To further convey the degradation in bubble size distribution with pressure, bubble diameter data are normalized (D/D_0 where D_0 is the initial bubble diameter at time zero) as shown in Figure 8c. The resulting D/D_0 distribution data

show that in general bubble size increases more slowly at higher pressure. Bubble size increases significantly at $p = 0$ bar in 60 min, especially for bubble sizes below 50% smaller. Figure 8d shows the average bubble diameter (D_{ave}) at each pressure over time. The percent increase in D_{ave} with elapsed time decreases with increase in chamber pressure. For example, from $t = 0$ to 30 min, D_{ave} increases 118% at $p = 0$ bar, 72% at 2 bar and 56% at 4 bar. The result also reveals that the foam bubble degradation process is slower at higher pressure.

The bubble image analysis shows that foam bubbles are smaller and more uniform at higher pressure, and the growth in bubble size with time is noticeably slower with increase in chamber pressure. Based upon the foam degradation mechanisms, foam bubbles with uniform sizes are more stable due to less gas diffusion between bubbles. Another plausible explanation is that it takes more time for liquid to drain from smaller bubbles than from larger bubbles due to increased surface area, and therefore liquid drainage travel path is longer in smaller bubbles.

Figure 8. Bubble size analysis for $FER_p = 20$ foam at $p = 0, 2,$ and 4 bar pressures.

Changes in FER and liquid fraction ϕ were estimated from the pressure chamber tests and are shown in Figure 9a and b. These results show that chamber pressure significantly retards the increase in FER and decrease in liquid fraction over time. For example, Figure 9a shows that FER increases from 20 to 74 over 60 min at atmospheric pressure. At 4 bar, FER increases only from 20 to 34 over a 60 min period. Consistent with the ideal gas law prediction, foam compressibility (C_{foam}) reduces considerably with increased chamber pressure, as shown in Figure 9c.

Figure 9. Influence of pressure on FER , liquid fraction, and compressibility for $FER_p = 20$ foam at $p = 0, 2,$ and 4 bar gauge pressures.

4. Influence of Foam Expansion Ratio on Foam Behavior

To investigate the influence of FER on foam behavior, a series of tests was conducted on foam with $FER_p = 10$ to compare with $FER_p = 20$ test results. The influence of FER on bubble size distribution is first presented. Figure 10a and b show the comparison of bubble images at $t = 0$ min for the two foam samples at $p = 0, 2$ and 4 bar. In general, there is little observed difference in bubble size for the two foams from the bubble images. Any difference in bubble size between the two foams would result from variations in foam generation pressure, air and liquid velocities and viscosity. In contrast to the significant influences of chamber pressure and types of foam generator on bubble size, test results reveal that the effect of FER on bubble size is negligible in this study. The corresponding cumulative bubble size distribution curves for the two foams at $t = 0, 30$ and 60 min are shown in Figure 10c. Both bubble size distribution curves shift to the right with time as bubbles grow due to coarsening, coalescence and liquid drainage. The growth of bubble size with time for both FER s can be also be examined by the normalized bubble size distribution as shown in Figure 10d. The magnitude of increase in bubble size for $FER_p = 10$ foam is noticeably more than for $FER_p = 20$ foam at pressures. The result reveals that $FER_p = 10$ foam bubbles degrade more quickly than $FER_p = 20$ foam. The findings are consistent with the results from Magrabi et al. (1999), which shows that bubble size growth in drier foam is not as significant as wet foam. According to Magrabi et al. (1999), liquid drainage plays a dominant role in controlling bubble growth in the initial stage of foam degradation process, and then both drainage and coalescence control and in the later phase only coalescence control bubble growth. As there is more liquid to drain for $FER_p = 10$ foam and thus bubbles grow in size more rapidly than the drier foam.

Figure 10. Comparison of bubble size distribution for $FER_p = 10$ and 20 foams under pressure.

Figure 11 shows the growth of average bubble size with time for both foams under pressure. The average $FER_p = 10$ foam bubble size in each condition is smaller than the average $FER_p = 20$ foam bubble size. At $p = 0$ bar, the difference between the average bubble sizes for the two foams become less over time. In addition, the percent increases in D_{ave} for $FER_p = 10$ foam with time in

the three pressure conditions are all larger than in the $FER_p = 20$ foam. For example, at $p = 0$ bar, D_{ave} of $FER_p = 10$ foam increases 232% in 60 min, while D_{ave} of $FER_p = 20$ foam increases 185%; at $p = 4$ bar, D_{ave} of $FER_p = 10$ foam increases 99% in 60 min and 92% for $FER_p = 20$ foam. The result reveal the bubble size growth for $FER_p = 10$ foam is more than $FER_p = 20$ foam, although its D_{ave} is less than $FER_p = 20$.

Figure 11. Average bubble diameter for $FER_p = 10$ and 20 foams with time under pressure.

Figure 12 presents the stability test results for the two foams under various pressures. The initial foam column heights in the pressure chamber were kept the same for both foams. Multiple tests were performed to insure repeatability in the results. As shown in Figure 12a, $FER_p = 10$ foam consistently shows greater liquid loss than $FER_p = 20$ foam at all pressures over time. This is expected because the $FER_p = 10$ foam is wetter. This can further be explained by the bubble size analysis result which shows that $FER_p = 10$ foam bubbles grow in size more rapidly than $FER_p = 20$ foam bubbles. The difference in liquid loss between the two foams becomes less with the increase in pressure. Foam volume loss for both foams at 0, 2, and 4 bar is shown in Figure 12b. In general, $FER_p = 10$ foam exhibits higher foam volume loss than $FER_p = 20$ foam, and the difference is more prominent at atmospheric pressure. Air volume loss of $FER_p = 10$ foam is slightly higher than $FER_p = 20$ foam (Figure 12c), but in general the values are negligible (less than 2%). Results from the pressure chamber tests are consistent with the bubble size analysis results for the two foams in the study.

Changes in FER and liquid fraction ($\varphi = FER^{-1}$) for the two foams with elapsed time are shown in Figure 12d and e, respectively. There is a sharp contrast in liquid fraction change in the two foams. The wetter $FER_p = 10$ foam loses liquid fraction at a significantly greater rate than the drier $FER_p = 20$ foam at all pressures. At $p = 0$ bar, there is a dramatic decrease in liquid fraction for $FER_p = 10$ foam in contrast to a gradual decline for $FER_p = 20$ foam. Similar trends are observed for the two foams at 2 and 4 bar. When combined with the image analysis results that show generally

similar bubble size behavior, these results suggest there is excess unnecessary liquid in $FER_p = 10$ foam.

The compressibility (C_{foam}) over time for the two foam samples show that $FER_p = 20$ foam is slightly more compressible than $FER_p = 10$ foam at all pressures (Figure 12f), as is expected, because $FER_p = 10$ foam lower air fraction than $FER_p = 20$ foam. The compressibility C_{foam} of the two foams become similar over time as the liquid fraction of the foams become closer. The pressure dependent C_{foam} increases slightly with time, mainly due to foam liquid loss with time that reduces the incompressible liquid fraction of the foam. Consequently, the volume fraction of air increases, resulting in an increase in C_{foam} .

Figure 12. Comparison of the pressure chamber test results for $FER_p = 20$ and 10 foams under pressure.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The results of a detailed study on foam stability have been described. A combination of macroscopic foam sample behavior tests, with elapsed time and at various pressures, together with microscopic bubble size analysis tests has revealed the time-dependent behavior of foam and the reasons for such behavior. The main findings include that liquid loss is significantly retarded at

higher chamber pressures, that foam volume loss accumulation is minimal over time compared to significant liquid volume loss observed, and that drier foam has a longer liquid drainage half life and improved liquid loss stability.

We observed that higher pressure environments yield smaller, more uniform foam bubbles. This uniformity and smaller bubble size leads to less diffusion and coalescence, as well as a longer, more tortuous drainage path. This is why liquid drainage is significantly slowed at higher chamber pressures.

Test results show that the influence of *FER* on bubble size is negligible in this study. The bubble image analysis shows that drier $FER_p = 20$ bubbles degrade more slowly over time compared to $FER_p = 10$ foam bubbles. Because drier foam has less liquid to drain and the gravity-driven liquid drainage plays a dominant role in the initial phase of foam aging. For similar reasons, drier foam accumulates less liquid loss than wet foam. These results suggest that there is excess unnecessary liquid in wetter $FER_p = 10$ foam.

An important practical finding from this study is that liquid volume loss accumulation, used in the tunneling industry as a measure of foam stability, is strongly influenced by pressure. The liquid loss half-life more than doubled from $p = 0$ bar (atmospheric pressure) to $p = 2$ bar. Because most if not all EPB soil conditioning occurs under pressures greater than atmospheric pressure and extending up to 5-6 bar, the liquid drainage half-life of foam in-situ is much greater than the EFNARC atmospheric pressure test indicates. To the effect that liquid loss half-life is used in design, this should be adjusted to the excavation chamber pressures anticipated along the tunnel project alignment.

Perhaps a more significant finding, however, is that liquid volume loss, the basis upon which the tunneling industry evaluates foam stability as evidenced by the EFNARC test, is not matched by appreciable foam volume loss. Despite the significant levels of liquid loss accumulation over elapsed time observed in all tests, foam volume loss was found to be minimal (less than one tenth of liquid loss) and air volume loss was found to be negligible (less than 2% over 60 minutes). This finding was made through a series of unload-reload tests over time in an attempt to agitate the foam and test its desired properties. Considering the intended goals of soil conditioning, the persistence of foam volume and more specifically occluded air volume within foam bubbles is what maintains the desired conditioned soil behavior. For example, the reduction in shear strength that leads to workability/flow, reduced abrasivity, torque, etc., is maintained by expanding soil particles to reduce interparticle friction. Reduced permeability is maintained by filling the soil voids with occluded air in bubbles. The persistence of these desirable engineering properties, i.e., the definition of stability, is directly controlled by the persistence of occluded air and not the liquid drainage. This calls into question the use of liquid loss as a measure of foam stability. Our findings suggest that

foam volume loss should be used as the more appropriate measure. The specifics of such a test could follow the procedure used in this study, including evaluation at the pore water and chamber pressures anticipated along the project alignment.

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Appendix 1: Influence of Foam Height on liquid drainage and Half-life

The EFNARC (2005) recommends method to characterize foam stability analysis via liquid drainage involves a 80 g foam sample placed in a filtered funnel. The time required for 40 ml of liquid to drain from the foam is the so called half-life. Previous research has shown that foam half-life is proportional to the height of foam column. The taller the foam column, the longer the half-life (Rand and Kraynik, 1983; Saint-Jalmes and Langevin, 2002). To investigate if foam height dominates half-life comparing to the influence of foam mass, a filtered funnel, a glass cylinder, and an acrylic pressure chamber with different dimensions (Figure. A1-1) were used to measure foam liquid drainage and half-life.

Figure A1-1. Devices for foam liquid drainage testing.

In accordance with EFNARC (2005), a 80 g foam sample with $FER = 15$ was prepared and placed into the filtered funnel ($D = 13$ cm). The measured initial foam height is 9 cm. The liquid drainage from the foam was measured with time. For comparison, an additional 80 g foam with the same concentration and FER was placed into the $D = 6$ cm cylinder. The resulting foam height is 42 cm. The test results are shown in Figure A1-2. The liquid drainage rate of the 42 cm tall, 6 cm diameter foam sample is much slower than that of the 9 cm tall, 13 cm diameter foam sample in the funnel, even though they have the same mass of foam. This is due to the difference in liquid drainage distance. Liquid drains due to gravity, so naturally the drainage time increases with foam height.

An additional 42 cm tall test was performed in the $D = 18$ cm cylinder. The measured liquid drainage data are very close to the test with the $D = 6$ cm cylinder. The results reveal that foam liquid drainage is not influenced by the mass of foam or the diameter of the sample. It is mainly affected by the foam column height for foam with the same properties. To further verify this conclusion, liquid drainage from $D = 6$ and 18 cm foam samples each with $H = 9$ and 20 cm was recorded as a function of time. The responses obtained from these tests clearly show that liquid drainage is dependent on sample height and independent of sample diameter. Foam samples with the same height but different diameters show similar liquid drainage curves. Therefore, it can be concluded that time dependent foam liquid drainage, including the so-called foam liquid half-life is influenced by the foam column height, not the mass of foam or the sample diameter.

Figure A1-2. Liquid drainage curves for foam with $FER = 15$ measured by a funnel with $D = 13$ cm, a cylinder with $D = 6$ cm and a cylinder with $D = 18$ cm.

Five additional foam liquid drainage tests with different foam heights ($H = 5, 15, 25, 30, 35$ cm) were conducted using the $D = 6$ cm cylinder to determine T_{50} (half-life) and T_{25} (quarter drain time). Combining with the previous testing results of $H = 9, 20,$ and 42 cm, the total eight sets of T_{50} and T_{25} data with different foam heights are shown in Figure A1-3. It presents that T_{50} increases with the increasing of initial foam height. As H changes from 5 to 42 cm, T_{50} increases from 16.8 to 37.5 min. It is obvious that the T_{50} and H have a non-linear relationship. Similar to T_{50} , T_{25} data also exhibit non-linear trend with H . The results confirms the findings from previous study (Rand and Kraynik, 1983; Saint-Jalmes and Langevin, 2002) that liquid drainage time increases with the increasing of foam column height. Based upon the above testing results, it can be concluded that the initial foam height is an important factor that influences foam liquid drainage. It should be considered in designing the laboratory testing for foam stability.

Figure A1-3. The influence of foam column height on foam half-life ($FER = 15$).

Appendix 2: Testing Procedures

The testing procedures for foam generation – pressure chamber – foam capture device are as follows:

- (1) Assemble the pressure chamber and set the scale: tighten the bolts and nuts of the chamber; place the chamber onto the scale, and then zero the scale.
- (2) Pressurized the chamber to the desired pressure: Open the valve that connects to the air supply line and pressurize the chamber to the desired pressure, use the back pressure regulator to control the chamber pressure. When the chamber pressure is stable, close the air supply valve.
- (3) Start generating foam: Input the desired air and liquid flow rates and start the foam generation program (LabVIEW) on the computer, open the bleeding off valve to flow foam into a bucket, and make sure the valve that connects to the pressure chamber is closed. Monitoring the pressures along the foam generation system (air-line pressure, pressure before the foam generator, and pressure after the foam generator).
- (4) Bleed off foam: When the pressures are stable, partially close the bleeding off valve and watch the pressure gage (next to the bleeding off valve) until the pressure reaches to the same pressure in the chamber. Adjust the liquid flow rate to keep it constant if it drops due to back pressure. Then fully close the bleeding off valve and open the valve which connects to the pressure chamber simultaneously.
- (5) Inject foam into the chamber: Foam flows into the pressure chamber after switching the valves. Watch the foam column height in the chamber and stop injecting foam when the height reaches 40 cm (here we propose 40 cm as the foam column height considering the

height of the chamber-45 cm, and the safety of the back pressure regulator on the chamber). Start timing when the foam injection process is completed.

- (6) Inject foam into the foam capture device: when foam is flowing into the pressure chamber, partially close the back pressure regulator (2-3 rotations) that is connected to the foam capture device to provide similar pressurized environment. Then open the valve that connects to the foam capture device to let foam flow through it. Adjust the pressure in the capture device the same as the chamber pressure. When there is steady foam flow through the capture device, stop the foam flow by closing both the upstream valve and the downstream back pressure regulator. Use the microscope to take foam bubble pictures automatically with elapsed time (i.e., $t = 0, 5, 10, \dots, 60$ min). The bubble images will be processed using a commercial image analysis software (AmScope) to obtain bubble sizes and bubble size distribution curves.
- (7) Calculate FER_p , volume of liquid (V_l) and height of liquid (H_l) for the foam sample in the pressure chamber: Record the mass of the foam in the chamber from the scale and calculate FER_p (at that certain pressure, p), V_l and H_l as follows:

$$FER_p = \frac{V_f}{V_l} = \frac{V_f}{M_l} = \frac{V_f}{M_f} \quad (\text{A-1})$$

$$V_l = \frac{V_f}{FER_p} \quad (\text{A-2})$$

$$H_l = \frac{V_l}{A} \quad (\text{A-3})$$

where V_f is the initial volume of foam in the chamber, and M_f is the mass of foam read from the scale, A is the cross-sectional area of the pressure chamber.

- (8) Record the height of foam and liquid with time: Record the height of foam, height of liquid accumulated at the bottom of the chamber with certain time intervals (i.e., 5 min). Determine liquid loss, foam loss, and air loss using Equation (1)-(3) as shown in the paper.
- (9) Test foam compressibility: Apply 1 bar extra air pressure to the foam sample to test its compressibility every 5 min, and then unload the air pressure to the original chamber pressure. Figure A2-1 shows an example of compressibility test for foam at $p = 0$ bar chamber pressure. Record the changes of foam height. Repeat this step for 60 min duration. Foam compressibility at time t can be calculated as shown in Equation (4) in the paper.

Figure A2-1. Pictures of compressibility test for foam at $p = 0$ bar pressure: (a) before applying 1 bar extra air pressure, (b) during applying 1 bar extra air pressure, and (c) after unloading the air pressure.

- (10) Discharge foam: When the test is completed, discharge the foam sample through the port at the bottom of the chamber. Release air pressure and get rid of the rest of foam in the chamber.